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Foreign Exchange Market Microstructure: A Theoretical Framework

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ABSTRACT

When we travel abroad to a foreign country, we have to exchange our domestic currency for that of the country we are visiting. For this purpose, we make use of exchange rates. However, exchanging currencies isn't just for travelers. The price difference is something you can trade. Frequent changes in the value of currencies on account of economic conditions, political news and interest rate changes drive foreign exchange trading and a trader's profit potential in the currency markets.

Just as any market provides a platform to facilitate exchange of a particular good/service between buyers and sellers, the foreign exchange market is also a medium through which participants can buy, sell, exchange and even speculate on currencies. The present paper broadly talks about the foreign exchange market, arbitrage strategies in the forex market, different exchange rate systems prevalent throughout the world, factors affecting exchange rate and modes of government/central bank intervention in the forex market.

Keywords: Exchange rate, foreign exchange market, arbitrage, intervention

1. INTRODUCTION

An exchange rate is the rate at which one country's currency can be converted into another. These rates are determined in the forex market. When a Japanese automobile manufacturer buys steel from India, he needs to convert yen to rupees (INR) to make the payment. In every exchange, prices need to be adjusted because one currency is typically weaker (has less value) while the other is stronger (has more value).

A decline in a currency's value is referred to as depreciation. Similarly, an increase in a currency's value is referred to as appreciation.

For example-

Yesterday, the exchange rate was \$1= ₹ 64

Suppose, today's exchange rate is \$1= ₹ 65

This means that the rupee has fallen in value (depreciated) and the US dollar has risen in value (appreciated) because now you have to pay more rupees to purchase dollars.

Let us understand two important trends in the market-

1. **Bull market-** A bull market is a market in which prices are rising or are expected to rise. It is characterized by optimism and investor confidence. Bull markets offer investors opportunities to earn

profits by buying financial instruments at a lower price and closing their position by selling at a higher price.

2. **Bear market-** A bear market is a market in which prices are falling or are expected to fall. It is characterized by pessimism and continuous selling which further pushes down the prices. Bear markets offer traders opportunities to sell at a higher price and close positions by buying at a lower price. In a bear market, traders sell to exit the market and minimize losses.

2.OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this paper is to provide a theoretical background of the foreign exchange market microstructure. It explains how exchange takes place in the foreign exchange market. This microstructure analysis will enable the readers to have an understanding of-

- Determinants of exchange rate,
- Arbitrage strategies in forex market,
- Exchange rate systems and
- Government intervention in foreign exchange market.

3.FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET

The foreign exchange market is very big. Unlike the stock and bond markets, forex market is open 24 hours a day and 5.5 days a week. It provides a platform for the purchase, sale, exchange and even speculation of currencies.

In this market, one currency is always strengthening against another (bullish), and therefore, one currency is always weakening against another (bearish). Because of this, you have equal opportunity to buy or sell to enter the market. So, if the US Dollar (USD) is strengthening against the Indian Rupee (INR), it implies that the Indian Rupee (INR) is weakening against the USD.

Scenario 1: Buy trade

If a trader believes that the euro is bullish against the US Dollar, i.e. the euro is strengthening against the USD, then he/she may enter a trade to buy euros, expecting to gain from the stronger value of euro compared to the US Dollar.

Scenario 2: Sell trade

Conversely, if a trader believes that the euro is bearish against the US Dollar, i.e. the euro is weakening against the USD, and then he/she may enter a trade to sell euros in the hope that the currency's value will become weaker compared to the US dollar.

4.ARBITRAGE IN FOREX MARKET

4.1 Meaning of Arbitrage

Markets are not always perfectly efficient. In such a situation, there can be discrepancy in the prices of two same assets. This results in arbitrage opportunities for traders.

Arbitrage refers to the practice of buying in one market and simultaneously selling in another, in order to capitalize on the price difference between two or more markets, the profit being the difference between the market prices. This profit is considered to be riskless for the trader. Hence, an arbitrage trader does not bear any market risk.

Arbitrage helps to correct the problem of pricing inefficiencies in the market. For this reason, these opportunities are often available for a very short-time, before being acted upon. Arbitrage currency trading

requires the availability of real-time pricing quotes. Traders must act quickly to capitalize on such opportunities. To help in finding these opportunities quickly, forex arbitrage calculators are often used.

4.2 Arbitrage Strategies in Forex Market

Forex Arbitrage involves the buying and selling of different currency pairs to exploit pricing inefficiencies. We can better understand arbitrage strategies by studying the following cases-

4.2.1 Case 1

Let's have a look at the following exchange rates-

$$\text{EUR/INR}=72.24$$

$$\text{EUR/USD}=1.12$$

$$\text{USD/INR}=65.46$$

In this case, a forex trader can buy one standard lot, i.e. 1,00,000 Euros for ₹72,24,000 INR. The trader can then sell the 1,00,000 Euros for \$1,12,000 USD. The \$1,12,000 USD can then be sold for ₹73,31,520 INR.

Hence, through the arbitrage process, the trader makes a profit of ₹1,07,520 INR per standard lot (₹73,31,520 - ₹72,24,000). The arbitrage process will continue until the pricing inefficiencies are completely eliminated.

4.2.2 Case 2- Arbitrage in Forex Futures Market

The possibility of pricing discrepancy also arises in case of forex futures market.

Suppose the following quotes are available:

$$\text{GBP/USD spot rate} = 1.51$$

$$\text{12-month GBP/USD futures contract trade at } 1.50$$

$$\text{12-month interest on USD is } 1.5\%$$

$$\text{12-month interest on GBP is } 3\%$$

A financial future is a contract to convert an amount of currency at a time in the future, at an agreed rate. Suppose the contract size is 1,000 units. If you buy one GBP/USD contract today, in 12-months time, you will receive £1,000 and give \$1,500 in return.

The arbitrageur thinks the price of the futures contract is too high. If he sells one contract, he will have to deliver GBP 1,000 in 12-months time, and in return will receive USD 1,500.

He does the following calculations:

To deliver £1,000, the arbitrageur needs to deposit £970.87 now for 12-months @ 3%.

He can borrow in US dollars the amount, \$1466.01 at 1.5% interest.

He can convert this to £970.87 at the spot rate.

The cost of the deal is \$1466.01 + \$21.99 (12-months interest @ 1.5%) = \$1,488.

The above deal would create a synthetic futures contract that would convert £1,000 to \$1488 in 12-months time. From this, he knows that the 12-month futures price should really be 1.488. The market quote is too high. He does the following trade:

Sell one futures contract @ 1.50.
 Create the synthetic futures deal as above

At the end of 12-months, under the contract he delivers £1,000 and receives \$1,500. Using the money, he pays back his loan of \$1,488(\$1466.01, plus \$21.99 interest). He makes a **riskless profit** of \$1,500 –\$1,488 = **\$12**.

Notice that the arbitrageur did not take any market risk at all. There was no exchange rate risk, and no interest rate risk. The deal was independent of both and the trader knew the profit from the outset.

The cash flows are shown in the Figure 1).

Figure1: Cash Flows in Futures Arbitrage

5. EXCHANGE RATE SYSTEMS

Exchange rate systems can be classified according to the degree of control exercised by the government/central bank of a country on exchange rates. The different exchange rate regimes are:

- Fixed exchange rate system
- Freely floating exchange rate system
- Managed float exchange rate system

- Pegged exchange rate system

5.1 Fixed Exchange Rate System

A fixed exchange rate regime is when a country holds its exchange rates constant or allows it to fluctuate only within a very narrow band. Out of the other exchange rate systems, this requires the maximum amount of government/ central bank intervention in order to maintain the currency's value within narrow boundaries.

An early form of fixed exchange rate was the 'gold standard' in which the value of all currencies was expressed in terms of gold.

Advantages of fixed exchange rates-

- a) It eliminates exchange rate risk and therefore, facilitates international trade between countries. Exporters and importers need not worry about adverse exchange rate movements.
- b) It facilitates investment flows between countries. Firms can engage in foreign direct investment without worrying about exchange rate movements of that currency.
- c) It reduces fluctuations and volatility in relative prices by bringing stability in exchange rates.
- d) It stimulates the economic growth of countries. Countries with fixed exchange rates are able to attract more funds as investment because the foreign investors do not have to worry about the currency weakening over time.

Disadvantages of fixed exchange rates-

- a) The government has to invest a lot of resources in maintaining huge foreign exchange reserves at all times in order to adjust and maintain exchange rates.
- b) Under fixed exchange rate system, automatic correction of imbalances in balance of payments of a country does not occur as the currency cannot appreciate/ depreciate as per the market forces.
- c) There is still a risk that the government will devalue or revalue the currency.

5.2 Freely Floating Exchange Rate System

A freely floating exchange rate regime is when the exchange rate values are determined by the forex market depending upon demand and supply conditions for that currency. In contrast to the fixed exchange rate system, this allows complete flexibility for exchange rate movements.

Advantages of freely floating exchange rate system-

- a) The government/ central bank is relieved of constantly maintaining exchange rates within specified boundaries. Thus, it need not invest a lot of resources in maintaining huge foreign exchange reserves at all times to implement intervention policies.
- b) According to economists, floating exchange rates enable a country to reduce the intensity of shocks and foreign business cycles and to forestall the possibility of having a balance of payment crisis. This is due to their ability to adjust automatically in response to market conditions.
- c) Countries are more insulated from inflation and unemployment problems in other countries. The exchange rate adjustments prevent the economic problems in one country from being 'exported' to other countries.
- d) It leaves monetary policies free to be used for other purposes such as stabilizing prices or employment in contrast to fixed exchange rates where monetary policy is committed to the single goal of maintaining the exchange rate.

Disadvantages of freely floating exchange rate systems-

- a) It leads to a lot of volatility and uncertainty in exchange rates, thereby bringing uncertainty into trade as well.
- b) The lack of stability brought about by floating exchange rates may discourage foreign direct investment into the country.
- c) A country's economic problems like unemployment and inflation can sometimes be compounded by freely floating exchange rates.

5.3 Managed Float Exchange Rate System

Sometimes, the central bank has to intervene to stabilize its country's currency. In such cases, the exchange rate regime lies somewhere between fixed and freely floating. It possesses features of both. The exchange rates are allowed to fluctuate and there are no official boundaries but the government can and sometimes does intervene in cases of extreme appreciation or depreciation of their currencies. This type of exchange rate system is known as a managed float. India too follows a managed float system.

5.4 Pegged Exchange Rate System

A pegged exchange rate system is one in which the home currency's value is attached or pegged to another country's currency or to an index of currencies. Countries commonly peg their currencies to that of a stable currency, like the US dollar because that makes the value of their own currency stable. For example, UAE's currency i.e. dirham is pegged to the US dollar at a peg rate of 3.6725 since 1997. It implies that dirham's value is fixed in terms of the US dollar and it moves in line against non-dollar currencies by the same degree as the dollar. Other currencies that are pegged to the US dollar are Saudi Arabia's riyal, Qatar's riyal, Hong Kong dollar.

Advantages of pegged exchange rate system-

- a) It facilitates trade and investment flows between the two countries with the pegged currencies by stabilizing the exchange rates between them.
- b) Currency pegs add long-term predictability for business planning between trading partners and can remain in force for decades.
- c) It helps provide security to small economies which may otherwise be unable to withstand exchange rate volatility.

Disadvantages of pegged exchange rate system-

- a) The country's government/central bank needs to maintain large amount of reserves in order to maintain the peg rate.
- b) Broken pegs can lead to major currency fluctuations, thus creating instability in the country's economy.
- c) Pegs which keep currencies artificially depreciated create an anti-competitive trading environment as compared to floating exchange rates. For e.g.: China's Yuan which was pegged to the US dollar from 1996 until 2005 was accused of being kept artificially low. This argument was brought about since the US was experiencing a huge trade deficit with China and domestic manufacturers argued that low-priced goods were costing jobs in the US.

6. GOVERNMENT INTERVENTION IN FOREX MARKET

Each country has a central bank that may intervene in the forex markets to control its currency's value.

For example: In the United States, the central bank is the Federal Reserve System (the Fed).

6.1 Reasons for Government Intervention

- **To smoothen the exchange rate movements-** If speculators are causing too much volatility in the currency market, then the central bank may intervene to smooth the currency movements over time. By reducing exchange rate uncertainty, the central bank will encourage international trade.
- **To establish implicit exchange rate boundaries-** The central bank may intervene to maintain its home currency rates within some unofficial or implicit boundaries. This is done to prevent a currency from falling below or rising above a particular benchmark value.
- **To lessen the impact of temporary disturbances-** The central bank may also intervene to counter disorderly market conditions.

For example: Suppose India exports majority of its goods to Country 'X'. Recently, a lot of political disturbances are going on in Country 'X' which has badly hit Indian exporters. In order to prevent the rupee's value from falling, the government may devalue its currency to boost Indian exports. The government, therefore, intervenes to offset the downward pressure on its currency (rupee, in this case) caused by such temporary disturbances.

6.2 Types of Government Intervention

Government Intervention can be categorized into:

- Direct Intervention
- Indirect Intervention

6.2.1 Direct Intervention

Suppose the rupee is depreciating against the dollar. To strengthen the rupee, RBI can exchange dollars for rupees (buy rupees and sell dollars) in the foreign exchange market, thereby putting an upward pressure on the rupee.

For example: RBI has been intervening in the currency market since December 2011, when the rupee hit a record low, to stabilize the currency. A weaker currency pushes up the country's import bill-you pay more rupees for the same amount of dollars- and contributes to the current account deficit.

To push up the rupee, RBI stepped up its dollar sales.

Similarly, suppose the rupee is appreciating too much against the dollar. To force the rupee to depreciate, RBI can intervene directly by exchanging rupee that it holds as reserves for dollars (sell rupee and buy dollars) in the foreign exchange market. By flooding the market with rupees, the RBI puts a downward pressure on the rupee.

An important point to be noted is that the central bank's effectiveness to intervene directly depends, to a large extent, on the amount of forex reserves it can use. If the central bank has a low level of reserves, it may not be able to exert much pressure on the currency's value. Market forces would overwhelm intervention actions.

Central bank direct intervention is becoming less effective. International financial flows and volume of forex transactions now exceed the combined forex reserves of all central banks. As a result, the numbers of direct interventions have declined.

Direct Intervention can further be of two types-

1) **Non-sterilized Intervention:**

When a country's central bank intervenes in the foreign exchange market without adjusting for the change in money supply, it is referred to as nonsterilized intervention.

For example: Suppose the Chinese Yuan is appreciating too much due to the huge volumes of foreign institutional investments and high volumes of export. Too much appreciation in a country's currency

can adversely hit its exporters. Hence, the Chinese central bank may intervene to keep its currency's value low. To do so, it will start selling Chinese Yuan to buy dollars (China is the largest holder of dollar-backed US Treasury paper). Sale of Yuan will increase money supply in the Chinese economy and lead to inflation. This type of direct government intervention without adjustments for change in the money supply is known as nonsterilized intervention.

2) **Sterilized Intervention:**

When a country's central bank intervenes in the foreign exchange market and simultaneously engages in offsetting transactions in the bond markets, it is referred to as sterilized intervention.

As a result, the country's money supply remains unchanged.

Continuing with the above example, if the increase in money supply leading to rising inflation is viewed as unfavorable for the economy, the Chinese central bank will issue bonds to suck out this excess money supply.

Since this type of direct intervention makes adjustments for change in money supply, it is called sterilized intervention.

6.2.2 Indirect Intervention

The central bank of a country can also affect its currency's value indirectly by influencing the factors that determine it.

Factors affecting a currency's spot rate include:

- 1) **Relative inflation rate-** A high rate of inflation in a country is likely to have a negative impact on its exchange rate with other countries, other factors remaining constant. This is because a rise in inflation rate will lead to a rise in the demand for foreign goods (as they have now become cheaper as compared to domestic goods), therefore leading to a rise in the demand for foreign currency. In addition, there will be a fall in the demand for goods of the country where inflation is relatively high, thereby causing its currency to depreciate.
- 2) **Relative interest rate-** A relatively high interest rate may attract foreign investment, thereby increasing the currency's demand and value. However, relatively high interest rate may also reflect expectations of relatively high inflation which places a downward pressure on the country's currency. This may further discourage foreign investors from investing in securities denominated in that currency. Therefore, it is better to consider the real interest rate among countries as it adjusts the nominal interest rate for inflation:

$$\text{Real interest rate} \cong \text{Nominal interest rate} - \text{Expected inflation rate} \quad (\text{Fisher Effect})$$

Therefore, we can say that other things held constant, a relatively high real interest rate increases the currency's value.

- 3) **Relative income levels-** Other factors remaining constant, a relatively high level of income in a country is likely to have a negative impact on its exchange rate with other countries. This is because a rise in income levels will lead to a rise in the demand for goods/services, thereby increasing the imports from other countries. The increasing demand for foreign currency will place a downward pressure on the home currency's value. This impact on exchange rate has been considered in isolation to other factors. However, in reality, changing income levels can also affect exchange rates indirectly through their impact on interest rates. If this effect is considered and if the interest rate also rises, then it will have a positive impact on the country's exchange rate. The actual impact, however, depends on the force of the resulting change.

- 4) **Government controls-** The government may intervene in the forex market in many ways:
 - a) Buying and selling currencies in the forex market.
 - b) Controlling macro-economic variables such as interest rates, income levels and inflation rate.
 - c) Imposing foreign trade and foreign exchange barriers.For example: If the Indian government imposes a heavy tax on goods imported from China, then it could discourage Chinese imports which could further discourage the exchange of rupees for Yuan.

- 5) **Expectation of future exchange rates-** The foreign exchange market also reacts to any news which might have a future impact on exchange rates. For instance, the implementation of the Goods and Services Act (GST) in India raised concerns of a potential surge in inflation in the Indian economy. Such news may cause currency traders to sell rupees, anticipating a future decline in the rupee's value. This may place an immediate downward pressure on the rupee. Similarly, if speculators anticipate rupee appreciation, then they can place upward pressure on the rupee's value.

Thus, under indirect intervention, the central bank can influence the above mentioned variables which in turn would affect the exchange rate.

Government Control of Interest Rates-

Consider the following example: If RBI wants the rupee to appreciate; it will hike the interest rates. As a result, foreign investors will transfer funds to India to capitalize on higher interest rates in India (high interest rates will also discourage borrowing and control inflation). Increasing investments will lead to more demand for rupees and hence put an upward pressure on its value. As a result, the rupee will appreciate.

Central banks have commonly raised their interest rates if their country experiences a currency crisis in order to prevent a major outflow of funds from the country.

However, a common problem is that many a times, indirect intervention not only failed to prevent the withdrawal of funds, it also increased the financing rate by firms in the country. This can cause the economy to weaken further.

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

An exchange rate is the rate at which one country's currency can be converted into another. Just like stock trading, there are bulls and bears in the foreign exchange market. A bull market is characterized by optimism and investor confidence while a bear market is characterized by pessimism. In a bear market, traders sell to exit the market and minimize losses. The eight most traded currencies in the forex market are U.S. dollar (USD), Canadian dollar (CAD), Euro (EUR), British pound (GBP), Swiss franc (CHF), New Zealand dollar (NZD), Australian dollar (AUD) and Japanese yen (JPY).

Arbitrage refers to the practice of buying in one market and simultaneously selling in another, in order to capitalize on the price difference between two or more markets, the profit being the difference between the market prices. The arbitrageur earns a riskless profit. Foreign exchange arbitrage involves the buying and selling of different currency pairs to exploit pricing inefficiencies.

Exchange rate systems can be classified according to the degree of control exercised by the government/central bank of a country on exchange rates. Each exchange rate system has its own advantages and disadvantages; therefore it is difficult to say which exchange rate regime is the ideal one. Each country has a central bank that may intervene in the forex markets to control its currency's value. The central bank may intervene to smoothen exchange rate movements, establish implicit exchange rate boundaries and to lessen the impact of temporary disturbances.

This paper is a preliminary study of the theoretical ideas that underlie the foreign exchange market microstructure. Thus, further research may be undertaken to examine the trading mechanisms, bid-ask spreads and volatility in the forex market. Empirical analysis may also be undertaken for the same.

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